

Data Management and Governance Plan for the Implementation of Constituency Development Funds (CDF) Electrification Projects in Zambia

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Executive Summary

Rural electrification plays a critical role in improving service delivery, economic productivity, and social development in Zambia. Under the Constituency Development Fund (CDF), Local Authorities are mandated to implement electrification projects across all constituencies. While this decentralised approach promotes local ownership, it has also resulted in fragmented data management, inconsistent reporting practices, limited project visibility, and weak coordination across institutions.

The purpose of this Data Management and Governance Plan is to establish a structured, standardised, and digitally enabled framework for managing data related to CDF-funded electrification projects throughout the project lifecycle. The Plan assesses existing data management practices and proposes a centralised governance model anchored at the Rural Electrification Authority, integrated with the SMART Zambia CDF Dashboard and supported by geospatially enabled systems.

Key findings indicate that reliance on manual and uncoordinated data processes undermines data quality, traceability, and effective monitoring. The Plan demonstrates that the adoption of standardised data collection tools, clear institutional roles, and governed digital workflows can significantly improve transparency, accountability, and evidence-based decision-making.

It is recommended that the framework be implemented in a phased manner, supported by sustained capacity building, dedicated operational funding, and alignment with national digital governance standards. Full implementation of this Plan will enhance coordination, improve oversight, and maximise the developmental impact of CDF electrification investments in Zambia.

1 Introduction

Rural electrification is a key driver of socio-economic development, supporting improved service delivery in health, education, and local economic activities. In Zambia, the Rural Electrification Authority (REA) is mandated to coordinate and provide technical oversight for electrification initiatives in rural and peri-urban areas (Government of the Republic of Zambia, 2013). Through the Constituency Development Fund (CDF), Local Authorities are empowered to implement priority development projects, with each of the country's 156 constituencies, administered through 116 districts, required to allocate a minimum of ZMW 1 million annually towards rural electrification. While this decentralised approach enhances local ownership, it also presents challenges related to coordination, data consistency, and effective project tracking across institutions.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this Data Management and Governance Plan is to establish a structured framework for managing data related to CDF-funded electrification projects. The plan applies to electrification of priority rural electrification projects using grid extensions, solar home systems, and solar mini-grids technologies, and covers the full project lifecycle from identification and feasibility assessment to implementation, monitoring, and commissioning. It supports the transition from fragmented manual records to a centralised digital system integrated with the SMART Zambia CDF Dashboard. The figure 1 shows the boundaries of Constituencies.

Figure 1: Constituency Boundaries in Zambia

1.2 Objectives and Aims

The main objective of this plan is to strengthen coordination, transparency, and accountability in the implementation of CDF-funded electrification projects through improved data governance and digitalisation.

The specific aims are to:

- i. Standardise data collection and reporting processes across all Local Authorities;
- ii. Establish a centralised and secure digital source for CDF electrification project data;
- iii. Improve data quality, consistency, and traceability across the project lifecycle;
- iv. Enable geospatial analysis to support appropriate technology selection and planning and visualisation;
- v. Facilitate real-time monitoring of project implementation and outcomes; and
- vi. Strengthen institutional coordination and data sharing among Ministry of Energy (MOE), REA, Local Authorities, ZESCO Limited, and Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development (MLGRD).

2 Methodology

This methodology describes the approach adopted for the design and implementation of the Data Management and Governance plan for CDF electrification projects. The methodology combines digital system design, structured data governance principles, and workflow automation to support decentralised project implementation while maintaining central coordination and oversight REA.

2.1 Tools Implemented

The methodology adopts a hybrid digital architecture that integrates offline field data collection with centralised data governance and national reporting platforms. The digital tools implemented as part of this methodology and their respective functions are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Digital Tools Used in the Data Management Framework

SN	Tool / Platform	Role	Governance Value
1	Kobo Collect	Field-level data capture	Enforces standardised data entry, GPS capture, and photo evidence at source
2	ODK Central	Central intake and control	Provides user management, audit logs, and form version control
3	PostgreSQL / PostGIS	Authoritative data repository	Maintains single source of truth with integrity and spatial controls
5	SMART Zambia CDF Dashboard	National reporting layer	Enables transparency, aggregation, and policy oversight

2.2 Key Assumptions

This methodology adopted the following assumptions for the data management and governance plan.

- i. REA is the system owner and custodian of all data related to CDF electrification projects;
- ii. Local Authorities are responsible for submitting accurate and complete project information; and
- iii. REA and local authorities are assumed to have basic ICT infrastructure and capacity to operate the system.

3. Governance Framework

The implementation of the Data Management and Governance framework resulted in a streamlined, end-to-end digital pipeline for CDF electrification projects. The figure 2 summarises the interactions between tools used.

Figure 2: Data flow diagram for CDF Projects

2.3 Data Sources and Institutional Roles

As outlined in table 2, data sources are aligned to specific project stages and institutional mandates. Project identification data is obtained from Local Authorities, while feasibility and scoping data are collected through joint field assessments by REA, Local Authorities, and ZESCO. Implementation data is generated through routine inspections and progress monitoring led by REA in collaboration with Local Authorities. Reporting data consists of aggregated indicators, dashboards, and spatial outputs compiled by REA and SMART Zambia to support monitoring and evaluation.

Table 2: Data Sources and institutional Roles for CDF Electrification Projects

SN	Project Stage	Data Type	Description	Responsible Institution
1	Project Identification	Project submission data	Administrative and initial technical project information	Local Authorities/MLGRD
2	Feasibility & Scoping	Field scoping data	Technical, socio-economic, and spatial assessment data	REA / Local Authorities/ZESCO
3	Implementation	Inspection and progress data	Monthly progress, cost, and status updates	REA / Local Authorities
4	Reporting	Aggregated indicators	KPIs, dashboards, and maps	REA / SMART Zambia

2.4 Components of the Governance Data Processes

Data processes define how information is created, validated, transformed, stored, shared, and archived across the lifecycle of CDF electrification projects. Within this Governance Plan, data processes are standardised, documented, and controlled to ensure consistency, accountability, and traceability across all participating institutions.

2.4.1 Data collection

Data creation occurs primarily at the Local Authority and field level during project identification, feasibility assessments, and implementation monitoring. Standardised digital forms, designed and approved by REA, govern the data elements to be captured, including administrative details, technical specifications, financial information, and geospatial coordinates. Mandatory fields, validation rules, and controlled form versions ensure that data quality is enforced at source.

2.4.2 Data Validation and Quality Assurance

To ensure accuracy, consistency, and standardisation of CDF electrification data, validation rules are applied to each data field at the point of submission. These rules define the required data type, acceptable values, and mandatory constraints, and are enforced through digital data collection tools and database controls. Where applicable, controlled selection lists are used to align submissions with official administrative and sector classifications

2.4.3 Data Integration and Transformation

Validated data is integrated into the central REA PostgreSQL/PostGIS database through controlled Extract Transform Load (ETL) processes. During integration, data is transformed to conform to national data standards, harmonised coding structures, and geospatial reference systems. This step ensures interoperability with national platforms and supports aggregation across constituencies and districts.

2.4.4 Data Storage and Maintenance

The REA PostgreSQL/PostGIS database serves as the authoritative repository for all CDF electrification data. Data integrity is maintained through relational constraints, role-based access control, and audit logging and fed into the PostgreSQL schema shown in figure. Routine database maintenance, backups, and performance monitoring are conducted to ensure data availability, reliability, and long-term preservation.

Figure 4: Cdf electrification database schema

2.4.5 Visualizing the Results in QGIS

Once the data is mapped, the **PostGIS** geometry column (geom) allows for instant visualization in QGIS. By connecting QGIS directly to the PostgreSQL database, REA planners can see a real-time Project Status Map.

2.4.6 Data Access, Use, and Sharing

Access to data is governed by clearly defined roles and permissions. Local Authorities can access and update data relating to their jurisdictions, while REA maintains full oversight and analytical access. Aggregated and approved datasets are shared with authorised institutions, including the Ministry of Energy and SMART Zambia Institute, through secure interfaces and dashboards to support planning, reporting, and policy oversight.

2.5 Principles Governing Data Management

To ensure the integrity of the CDF electrification data, the following guiding principles are adopted:

- i. **Data as a Strategic Asset:** Data is recognized as a critical resource for national planning and must be managed to maximize its value to the Republic of Zambia.

- ii. **Accountability and Ownership:** REA serves as the primary custodian and system owner. Local Authorities are accountable for the accuracy and completeness of the data submitted at the source.
- iii. **Transparency and Openness:** Data should be accessible to authorized stakeholders to promote oversight, while maintaining necessary security protocols.
- iv. **Interoperability:** Systems are designed to align with national digital governance standards to ensure seamless data exchange with the SMART Zambia Institute.
- v. **Quality at Source:** Validation rules are enforced during the initial data entry phase to prevent "garbage in, garbage out" scenarios

3 Policies and Standards

The Data Governance Plan for CDF electrification projects is informed by national legislation and established data governance literature, which collectively define requirements for lawful data processing, institutional accountability, interoperability, and information security. In Zambia, public sector data management must comply with statutory obligations on data protection, electronic government interoperability, and sector-specific mandates that assign custodianship and oversight responsibilities (Government of the Republic of Zambia, 2021; Government of the Republic of Zambia, 2023). These legal requirements are reinforced by international best practices in data governance and data quality management, which emphasise standardisation, accountability, security, and lifecycle-based data controls as prerequisites for effective public sector decision-making (DAMA International, 2017; ISO, 2015). Alignment with national digital governance frameworks further ensures interoperability and consistency across government systems (SMART Zambia Institute, 2020).

Table 3 presents the ISO standards that will guide auditable internal data management workflows

Table 3: Data Governance Plan and management standards

Standard	Focus Area	Application in CDF Projects
ISO/IEC 38505-1	Data Governance	Framework for evaluating, directing, and monitoring the use of data by REA.
ISO 8000	Data Quality	Ensures that GPS coordinates and technical specs meet accuracy and completeness thresholds.

ISO/IEC 27001	Information Security	Governs the security of the PostgreSQL database, including encryption and access control.
ISO 19115	Geographic Metadata	Standardizes how GPS and mapping data (spatial data) are described in the system.

4 Funding Breakdown

The financial strategy for this data governance plan is divided into Operational and Developmental streams:

i. Government/REA (Operational)

Focuses on long-term maintenance (OPEX). This includes hosting at the National Data Centre for legal compliance, software subscriptions (ODK, Django), and salaries for a dedicated Data Governance Unit to oversee system integrity.

ii. Cooperating Partners (Scaling)

Focuses on the initial build and expansion (CAPEX). Partners like the World Bank, EU, and JICA provide grants for system upgrades, ruggedized mobile hardware for field teams, and connectivity infrastructure (satellite/Smart Village kits) for remote data syncing.

5 Capacity Building Plan

The successful implementation of the data management framework depends on the competencies of the personnel operating it. To address this, a tiered capacity-building programme has been established, as summarised in Table 4.

Table 4:Capacity Building needs for data management

SN	Target Group	Focus Area	Tools
1	Local Authorities	Project entry, submission rules, and status tracking.	ODK/KoboToolbox
2	Field Officers (REA/ZESCO)	Offline data capture, GPS tagging, and photo evidence.	ODK/KoboToolbox
3	REA Data Analysts	Advanced SQL querying, QGIS visualization, and reporting.	PostgreSQL / QGIS

6 Risk Management and Mitigation

The table below 5 shows the risk and mitigation matrix for the data governance plan in managing CDF electrification projects

Table 5: Risk and Mitigation Matrix

SN	Risk Category	Risk Description	Risk Level	Mitigation Measures
1	Data Quality Risk	Incomplete, inaccurate, or inconsistent data submitted by Local Authorities	High	Enforce mandatory validation rules, controlled selection lists, and automated checks at data entry; conduct periodic data quality audits and refresher training
2	Capacity Risk	Limited technical and digital skills among Local Authority and field officers	High	Implement tiered capacity-building programme; adopt Training-of-Trainers (ToT) model; provide user manuals and helpdesk support
3	Data Security Risk	Unauthorised access, data breaches, or loss of sensitive information	High	Apply role-based access control (RBAC), encryption in transit and at rest, regular security audits, and compliance with ISO/IEC 27001
4	Sustainability Risk	Dependence on donor funding for system operation and maintenance	High	Integrate operational costs into REA recurrent budget; leverage National Data Centre hosting
5	System Adoption Risk	Resistance to use of digital tools in favour of manual processes	Medium	Link data submission compliance to project approval and reporting requirements; provide change-management support and incentives
6	Connectivity Risk	Poor or unreliable internet connectivity in rural areas	Medium	Use offline-capable data collection tools (ODK/Kobo); enable delayed synchronisation; 7provide periodic physical data syncing options
7	Data Loss Risk	Loss of data due to hardware failure or system outages	Medium	Implement automated daily backups, off-site storage, and disaster recovery procedures

8	Interoperability Risk	Failure to integrate with SMART Zambia or other government systems	Medium	Adhere to SMART Zambia interoperability standards; use standard APIs and data formats
9	Institutional Coordination Risk	Unclear roles and responsibilities among REA, Local Authorities, and partners	Medium	Formalise roles through governance framework, SOPs, and data-sharing agreements
10	Legal & Compliance Risk	Non-compliance with data protection or public sector ICT regulations	Low	Ensure alignment with Data Protection Act, Electronic Government Act, and regular compliance reviews

7 Conclusion

This Data Management and Governance Plan establishes a structured and standardised framework for improving the coordination, transparency, and accountability of CDF-funded electrification projects in Zambia. By integrating digital data collection, validation, centralised storage, and geospatial analysis under the custodianship of the REA, the Plan addresses longstanding challenges of fragmented data and limited national oversight. Alignment with national legislation, SMART Zambia standards, and international best practices ensures auditability and interoperability. It is recommended that implementation be phased, supported by sustained capacity building and dedicated operational funding, to embed data governance as a core enabler of effective and equitable rural electrification delivery

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